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What drives profits in savings groups? Bayesian data mining evidence from the SAVIX database

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Abstract

Savings groups provide savings and loans to low-income individuals in rural and peri-urban areas. This study applies Bayesian data mining methods to a database of more than 200,000 savings groups with the aim of identifying which micro, meso, and macro factors are associated to profit generation in the groups. The results show that the facilitation mechanisms of development agencies and the macro-economic environment are more important than internal group dynamics for profit generation. The findings suggest that the focus of development agencies on bottom-of-the-pyramid groups creates wealth for communities in countries with a more dispersed and rural population. However, the generation of profits depends on the graduation of groups and the facilitation model implemented by a development agency.

Keywords: Savings groups; development agencies; Bayesian model averaging

JEL Classification: G21, O12, C11

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1 Introduction

Financial inclusion alleviates poverty and promotes economic growth through a process of capital distribution among low-income individuals (Mader, 2018). Despite the relevance of financial inclusion, there is still a gap of over 1.7 billion people in the world who lack access to formal financial services (Demirguc-Kunt et al., 2018). Savings groups fill this gap by providing informal financial services to the poor in rural and peri-urban areas.

In savings groups, group members pool their savings into two funds: a collective fund to provide loans, and a welfare fund that supports members during emergencies (see details about savings groups in Appendix A). The informal lending of savings groups complements the formal lending of microfinance institutions, such as the ones described in Mukherjee (2020) or Regmi et al. (2020). The welfare fund of savings groups is a risk-coping strategy that complements formal insurance mechanisms, such as those described in Goodwin and Piggott (2020), Belissa et al. (2021) or Zhang and Palma (2021).

Over 100 million individuals living in 10.5 million households worldwide participate in savings groups (Greaney et al., 2016; Burlando and Canidio, 2017). Given the informal nature of these groups, however, standardized information about these associations is scarce. The Savings Groups Information Exchange (SAVIX) is the first database to provide extensive information about thousands of these groups around the world. In this study, Bayesian data mining methods are applied to the SAVIX to identify which variables are related to profit generation in savings groups. Profit generation is measured by the return on savings of a group¹.

The results indicate that profit generation in savings groups is mainly associated to external institutional factors—the macroeconomic environment and the facilitation model of non-governmental organizations (NGOs)—as opposed to the internal micro level characteristics of a group. Micro variables such as member attendance and gender composition are not the most relevant variables for profit generation, as they only account for 21% of variance in returns. By contrast, the facilitation model of NGOs working with the groups

¹ While the SAVIX has been partly used to evaluate group performance in Cambodia (LeGrand et al., 2018), Kenya and Uganda (Witbooi and Marwa, 2018), to our knowledge our study is the first one that rigorously analyzes the complete SAVIX database with the aim of understanding the different factors affecting profit generation in savings groups worldwide.

explains 53% of returns, and the macroeconomic environment is related to 26% of variation in returns.

In macroeconomic terms, groups located in countries with a more dispersed and rural population show higher returns, thus suggesting that the focus of NGOs on bottom-of-the-pyramid groups in rural communities has been successful in the creation of wealth for low-income individuals. Groups that graduated from the supervision of a facilitating agency also show higher returns compared to groups that are still supervised. This indicates that the savings group model of financial intermediation in rural communities has growth potential over time, even after development actors stop working with a group.

The results of our study help fill the research gap left by qualitative and context-specific studies of saving groups, which produced results that cannot be generalized beyond the local context². Our results provide valuable large-sample evidence for NGOs working with savings groups as a platform to promote financial inclusion and sustainable development in communities at the bottom of the wealth pyramid.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 discusses profit generation in savings groups and the variables that could influence profit generation. Section 3 describes the methodology used in the study. Section 4 presents the results, and Section 5 provides concluding remarks.

2 Profit generation in savings groups

The performance of savings groups is commonly measured by loan repayment (Ugbomeh et al., 2008), the debt-to-equity ratio (Hendricks and Chidiac, 2011), accumulated savings, number of loans disbursed, average loan size, loan default rates (Feigenberg, Field, and Pande, 2013), savings and credits per member (Lowicki-Zucca et al., 2014), larger volumes of savings and credit allocation (Ksoll et al., 2016), cumulative savings, loans disbursed, return on savings, and default rates (Burlando and Canidio, 2017).

² Flynn and Sumberg (2018) use interviews to analyze the activities of 57 members of youth savings groups in Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia, and Ghana, while Le Polain, Sterck, and Nyssens (2018) use qualitative methods to analyze savings groups in the Congo. Armendáriz and Morduch (2010) argue that qualitative and context-specific studies are not a substitute for statistical evidence based on large samples, such as the evidence presented in this paper.

In this study, return on savings (ROS) is used to measure profit generation in savings groups³. In the ROS indicator, returns are calculated by adding the values of the cash kept in the cashbox (*cash*), the bank balance (*bankbal*), the property of the group at the end of the cycle (*propend*), and the loans outstanding (*loans*). From the sum of these values, the value of the savings (*savings*), the property of the group at the start of the cycle (*propstart*), and the debts of the group (*debts*) are deducted. ROS is calculated by dividing the returns by half of the value of the savings in a group:

$$ROS = \frac{(cash + bankbal + propend + loans) - (savings + propstart + debts)}{savings/2}$$

The adjustment of the denominator to half of the savings is proposed in Rasmussen (2012, equation 5). Rasmussen argues that the division of the stock of savings by half brings ROS closer to the profile of profit generation in savings groups, as the funds of savings groups are not available at the beginning of the cycle of operation.

Profit generation can be influenced by micro, meso, and macro factors. Micro factors are related to group-level characteristics. Macro factors reflect the macroeconomic environment where a group operates. Meso factors are related to the facilitation model of international development agencies working with savings groups. At the micro level, the variables considered in this study are: members' attendance, the dropout rate, the number of loans outstanding per member (Ugbomeh et al., 2008; Lowicki-Zucca et al., 2014), the percentage of female members in a group, the group size (the number of members; see Bisrat et al., 2012), the number of accumulated loans per member, the amount in the welfare fund per member (in US dollars), the fund utilization rate, and a dummy variable equal to 1 for urban or peri-urban groups and equal to 0 for groups in rural regions (Christensen, 1993). The selection of micro variables is based on Burlando and Canidio (2017), Annan et al. (2013), Ledgerwood et al. (2013), Maliti (2017), Le Polain et al. (2018), and Baland et al. (2019).

Regarding meso factors, the variables included in the analysis are the provision of plus social services, the assistance of a facilitating agency working with a group, the group status (active, graduated, supervised), and the type of group formation (formation by a field officer, a village agent, a group-paid agent, a project-paid agent, an unpaid agent, an apprentice, or

³ Similar results were obtained using returns on assets as a performance metric of profit generation, see Appendix B for details.

spontaneous formation). The importance of a development agency working with a group was highlighted by Beaman, Karlan, and Thuysbaert (2014).

The macro variables considered as potential drivers of returns are the macroeconomic uncertainty in a country (measured as the average country inflation over the past five years), the inflation rate, the age-dependency ratio, the level of inequality (measured with the Gini coefficient), financial deepening, the literacy rate, GDP per capita (in constant USD of 2010), the population density, the percentage of rural population, the poverty headcount ratio, and GDP growth (annual percentage). Evidence of a positive association between economic growth and savings is provided by Attanasio, Picci, and Scorcu (2000) and Deaton and Paxson (2000).

Other macroeconomic variables may not affect returns directly but have an indirect effect on savings accumulation. Income, for example, is an important determinant of savings in the studies of Collins (1991), Edwards (1995), and Schmidt-Hebbel and Servén (2000). Population density and the percentage of the rural population in a country can affect returns because transport costs increase the chances of members not contributing with their savings and/or not paying their debts to the group (Christensen, 1993). Levenson and Besley (1996) show that there is a link between the age of the population living in a country and participation in savings groups. Finally, Mutebi et al. (2017) note that low literacy levels among members is one of the challenges faced by savings groups. Table C in Appendix C summarizes all the potential explanatory variables of profit generation in savings groups considered in the study.

3 Methodology

Bayesian data mining is applied to identify which micro, meso, and macro variables are associated to profit generation in savings groups. Data mining is the process of exploring a large dataset with the aim of discovering unknown patterns and identifying associations through statistical and mathematical techniques (Larose and Larose, 2014). The Cross Industry Standard Process for Data Mining (CRISP-DM) is a process to extract knowledge of a database using data-mining, which can be summarized in five stages (Feyyad, 1996): selection (creating a target dataset on which discovery is to be performed), pre-processing (cleaning the data from noise and outliers), transformation of data (for dimensionality reduction or comparability), data mining (searching for patterns using a particular statistical technique), and the evaluation and interpretation of mined patterns. In this study, the CRISP-DM process is adapted to analyze the SAVIX: in the selection stage, the relational SQL tables

of the SAVIX were joined into a single table that was combined with the external database of the World Bank's World Development Indicators. During the pre-processing stage, the SAVIX database was cleaned from outliers, and duplicate or unrealistic records were removed from the database. Winsorizing at the 1th and 95th percentile was applied for the target dependent variable (returns on savings), and at the .5th and 99.5th percentile for the explanatory variables. Observations with unrealistic values as e.g. negative assets were dropped from the database. Additionally, groups with less than 3 members and more than 100 members were removed from the database used in the analysis. This last trimming preserves the community nature of savings groups, since as noted by Bisrat, Kostas, and Feng (2012), in large groups individuals that do not have close relationships might change the focus of savings groups to a bank-like profit-oriented role (see Calomiris and Rajaraman, 1998), while in contrast small savings groups are started based on strong ties like friendship, business associates, school mates or within the neighborhood. During the transformation stage, the categorical data of the SAVIX was dichotomized with one-hot encoding and the continuous variables were transformed by subtracting each variable by its mean and dividing the results by the standard deviation of the variable. This transformation standardizes the results to properly compare the importance of each variable for profitability, since due to the standardization the estimated coefficients of the data-mining model will be all measured in standard deviations.

Bayesian methods and panel regressions were applied to the transformed data set in order to discover relationships between profits and group level characteristics at micro level, group facilitation at meso level, and the macroeconomic environment. Specifically, Bayesian Modeling Averaging (BMA) was applied to select the explanatory variables to be included in the panel regression. BMA was used to identify relevant explanatory variables from a large set of potential covariates in Sala-i-Martin et al. (2004), Masanjala and Papageorgiou (2008), Ley and Steel (2009), Eicher et al. (2011), Eriş and Ulaşan (2013), Magnus and Wang (2014) and Katayama et al. (2019). BMA is an appropriate method for analyzing the SAVIX database because BMA identifies explanatory patterns in the presence of large number of potential explanatory covariates. Rather than being based on a single model, BMA estimates thousands of different models with different combinations of explanatory variables, and then it summarizes all the results to obtain the probability of each variable being related to profit generation. Details of the BMA algorithm can be found in Appendix D.

The empirical strategy of the study follows three steps. First, all the potential micro, meso, and macro, drivers of profit generation are fed into the BMA algorithm. Next, BMA identifies

the variables with the highest probability of being related to profit generation in savings groups. Finally, a reduced panel regression model is estimated with the most important variables identified in the second step, in order to calculate what proportion of variation in group returns is explained by each regressor.

In the BMA algorithm, 8,000 potential combinations of micro, meso, and macro drivers are estimated to calculate the probability of each variable influencing ROS. In all the BMA models, control covariates are included to account for the heterogeneity of countries and back donors, as well as between-cycle and within-cycle (time in the cycle) fixed effects.

The reduced regression model only includes variables with a probability of 25% or higher of explaining profit generation in savings groups. The 25% threshold was chosen based on Bayes factors, which measure the strength of evidence of the reduced models against the complete model with all the variables included in the analysis; see Ly et al. (2016) and Appendix D for details.

4 Results

The SAVIX database has quarterly observations on more than 200,000 savings groups in 52 countries, between the years 2010 to 2017. Half of the groups in the SAVIX are located in eight African countries: Uganda (22,702 groups), Tanzania (21,374 groups), Mali (21,021 groups), Burkina Faso (13,680 groups), Ghana (12,337 groups), Mozambique (10,244 groups), Senegal (10,148 groups) and Kenya (8,906 groups).

The SAVIX information was cleaned to remove duplicate observations and outliers. Winsorizing at the 1st and 95th percentiles was applied to the target dependent variable (ROS), and at the 0.5th and 99.5th percentiles to the explanatory variables. The ROS of the groups in the cleaned SAVIX database is on average equal to 29% (median 21%) with an interquartile range of 1.72% to 45.5%. Descriptive statistics of the variables considered as potential drivers of ROS are shown in Tables 1.1 and 1.2. Table 1.1 shows statistics for continuous variables, and Table 1.2 show statistics for categorical and dichotomous variables.

Table 1.1 shows that there is a high commitment of the members participating in savings groups in the SAVIX. Members' attendance to the meetings is on average 91% (median 96%) and the dropout rate is only 1.8%. The high attendance rate and the low dropout rate can be explained by the enforcement mechanisms in savings groups (see Anderson et al., 2009), and

by the fact that members put their own money into the groups and receive fines if they do not attend the meetings. On average, the groups in the cleaned SAVIX database are composed of 21 members, with a minimum of five and a maximum of 34 members. Around 79% of members are women (median 87%), highlighting the prevalence of women in savings groups.

Table 1.1. Descriptive statistics of the continuous variables considered potential drivers of profit generation.

	Min	Median	Mean	Max	Obs
Group characteristics					
Member's attendance (%)	39.29	96	91.24	100	234,041
Dropout rate (%)	0	0	1.79	45	153,359
Number of loans per member	0	0.36	0.38	1	234,041
Women members in the group (%)	0	86.96	78.99	100	234,041
Group size (number of members)	5	21	21	34	153,359
Accumulated loans per member	0	0.30	0.75	133.33	165,340
Welfare fund per member (USD)	0	0.47	1.10	12.59	234,041
Fund utilization rate	0	40.44	41.25	100	116,718
Macroeconomic variables					
Macroeconomic uncertainty	0.54	3.51	4.08	14.36	234,033
Inflation rate (%)	-2.41	5.32	6.08	21.87	234,033
Age-dependency ratio	45.91	88.71	86.44	111.67	234,033
Inequality	31.03	41	41.54	63.20	196,367
Financial deepening	-2.55	23.24	29.65	179.77	220,998
Literacy rate (%)	15.46	67.09	58.73	96.40	209,273
GDP per capita (USD 2010)	218.30	712.6	1160.2	7575.2	234,033
Population density	12.35	73.86	105.28	459.88	233,868
Rural population	20.59	67.67	65.86	88.52	234,033
Poverty	17.70	36.10	36.97	71.20	204,654
GDP growth (%)	-3.92	5.41	5.49	20.72	234,033

Table 1.2. Descriptive statistics of the categorical variables considered potential drivers of profit generation.

	One	Zero
Group characteristics (peri-urban = 1, rural = 0)		
Location of savings groups	117,323	116,718
Group facilitation variables (codified as one)		
Provision of additional services	85,025	149,016
Provision of additional social services	25,799	208,242
Provision of additional financial services	14,733	219,308
No facilitating agency	18,127	215,914
Facilitating agency A	67,738	166,303
Facilitating agency B	26,803	207,238
Facilitating agency C	39,190	194,851
Facilitating agency D	21,893	212,148
Facilitating agency E	21,897	212,144
Status: active	102,358	131,683

Status: graduated	47,816	186,225
Status: supervised	74,519	159,522
Formation by field officer	9,356	224,685
Formation by village agent	120,478	113,563
Formation by group paid agent	30,712	203,329
Formation by project paid agent	41,484	192,557
Formation by unpaid agent	9,134	224,907
Formation by apprentice	7,890	226,151
Formation: spontaneous	567	233,474

Groups in the cleaned SAVIX database have, on average, an amount of savings per member equal to 29 USD (median 19 USD), with an inter-quartile range of 7.3 USD to 39.8 USD. The welfare fund in the groups is on average equal to 1.10 USD per member. Almost all the groups in the SAVIX database (92%) work with a facilitating agency (Table 1.2). Three quarters (75%) of the groups work with five development agencies: Aga-Khan Foundation, CARE, Oxfam, Plan International, and World Vision. (The names of these facilitating agencies are anonymized in Table 1.2.) In the SAVIX, 36% of the groups (85,025 groups) have records of receiving development services from NGOs, alongside savings and lending activities. Social services include training in climate change, agriculture, women’s empowerment, child protection, food security, nutrition, health, and water and sanitation.

Half of the groups in the SAVIX are located in peri-urban regions (117,323 groups). The rest of the groups operate in rural regions, which is consistent with the savings group model that promotes financial access to impoverished communities located in rural areas or urban slums. In the database, 76% of the groups are recorded as being either active (44%) or supervised (32%), while 20% are graduated and operate without close supervision by a facilitating agency. The groups in the dataset were mainly formed by field officers (51%), group-paid agents (18%), or village agents (13%).

Tables 2 and 4 summarize the results of estimating the association of ROS with microlevel characteristics, meso-level facilitation mechanisms of NGOs, and with the macroeconomic environment. Table 2 shows results for all the potential explanatory variables considered in the study. Table 4 shows a reduced model estimated with the variables that have a probability higher than 25% of explaining profit generation. Table 3 shows the values of the Bayes factors that are used to simplify the general BMA model of Table 2 to the reduced regression model estimated with the most important variables for profit generation in Table 4.

If only variables with a posterior inclusion probability (PIP) higher than 15% are selected for the reduced model (12 variables), a Bayes factor of 2.3859 is obtained, suggesting little evidence in support of a model based on a 15% probability threshold. A model with 10 variables with a posterior inclusion probability above 25% has the highest support, with a Bayes factor equal to 2.4657 (Table 4).

The results of the complete and reduced models show that ROS is mainly associated to meso and macro variables, which jointly explain 79% of profit generation in savings groups. 53% of profit generation is explained by meso variables linked with the group facilitation mechanisms of development agencies. The macroeconomic environment explains 26% of performance, while group characteristics explain the remaining 21% of variation in profit generation (Table 3). The most important meso variables for profit generation are the type of development agency working with a group, the group status—graduated—and the provision of additional development services.

With a probability of 26%, the facilitation model of development agency B increases ROS by two and a half percentage points. By contrast, with a probability of 96%, the model of agency D decreases ROS by 12 percentage points (Table 4). The higher returns of groups working with development agency B, compared to the negative effect on returns observed in groups working with agency D, can be explained by the prioritization of social outputs over financial gains in the case of agency D, or by the innovations in the basic savings group model implemented by agency B.

Graduated groups that are no longer under the supervision of a development agency have higher ROS, compared to supervised groups. Graduated groups have a probability of 72% of increasing returns, and in the reduced models graduated groups on average increase returns by nine percentage points, compared to groups with other statuses. The higher returns in graduated groups arise from learning effects and provide evidence of the financial sustainability of the savings group model, which persists and even increases after donor and program support has ended (Sinclair and Singh, 2015).

The higher returns of graduated groups also suggest that once facilitators leave the groups, members start to create more value. By contrast, supervised groups may be limited by the standardized facilitation models of NGOs, which may not allow groups to develop their full potential and maximize their wealth creation. Jahns and Wilson (2018) note that NGOs and donors tend to impose a default delivery model when supervising a group, even though a

standardized model does not always make sense in different contexts. Gugerty (2019) adds that a default “one size fits all” delivery model may impede development objectives if flexibility and customization are compromised. Danquah et al. (2018) highlight that a reason for program failure is that development projects are too top-down and need to be more bottom-up (i.e., with beneficiary involvement in the development process).

Table 2: BMA results: General model

	Bayesian point estimates	Probability of driving profit generation	Importance for profit generation (%)
Micro factors (group-level characteristics)			21.06
Members' attendance	0.0006	2.3273	0.3100
Dropout rate	0.0104	5.3539	1.1494
Number of loans outstanding per member	9.5990	55.7192	6.5517
Women members in a group	-0.0001	1.6563	0.0635
Group size	0.0055	3.5198	0.7553
Accumulated loans per member	7.5745	45.4549	5.3355
Welfare fund per member	0.4677	41.2770	4.5701
Fund utilization rate	-0.0064	9.4912	1.6251
Peri-urban savings groups	0.0656	3.6412	0.6985
Meso factors (group facilitation)			52.00
Provision of additional services	-0.5849	11.3580	1.8560
Provision of additional social services	-6.4915	68.6892	7.6767
Provision of additional financial services	1.0472	14.4235	2.1536
No facilitating agency	0.0117	2.7099	0.0866
Facilitating agency A	0.0515	2.6467	0.4308
Facilitating agency B	2.5021	26.5281	3.2839
Facilitating agency C	-1.3077	16.8697	2.4109
Facilitating agency D	-11.6309	96.1777	16.1800
Facilitating agency E	-0.4917	7.7627	1.4241
Group status: active	-3.3854	30.2865	3.9656
Group status: graduated	8.8459	72.2023	9.5944
Group status: supervised	-0.1522	3.7955	0.4794
Formation by field officer	-0.0148	2.2494	0.2860
Formation by village agent	-0.3563	3.1294	0.5738
Formation by group-paid agent	-0.0218	2.4676	0.3534
Formation by project-paid agent	-0.0664	2.7570	0.5488
Formation by unpaid agent	-0.0173	1.9471	0.1416
Formation by apprentice	-0.2029	2.7952	0.5143
Formation: spontaneous	-0.0093	2.2391	0.0445
Macro factors (macroeconomic environment)			26.94
Macroeconomic uncertainty	0.0032	2.2486	0.1160
Inflation rate	0.0006	2.4495	0.0633
Age-dependency ratio	0.0020	1.8517	0.1727
Inequality	-0.0233	3.4031	0.6604
Financial deepening	-0.0142	5.2619	1.0572
Literacy rate	-0.0134	3.8144	0.5963
GDP per capita	0.0006	6.1061	1.0036
Population density	-0.1987	96.0592	15.0254
Rural population	0.4897	46.5025	4.9910
Poverty (headcount rate)	-0.0139	3.0532	0.6720
GDP growth	0.1558	18.6345	2.5787

(*) In the data-mining models, control covariates were included to account for countries, donors, and between-cycles and within-cycle effects.

Table 3: Bayes factors used to select the threshold for the reduced model

PIP threshold	Variables	Bayes factor
>5%	19	1.9888
>15%	12	2.3859
>25%	10	2.4657
>35%	8	2.3829
>45%	7	2.3805
>55%	5	1.4036

Note: Bayes factor of the reduced models with 5–19 variables against the complete model with 39 variables

Table 4: Reduced model estimates

	Panel regression estimates*	Bayesian point estimates**	Importance for profit generation (%)
Micro factors (group-level characteristics)			21.32
Number of loans outstanding per member	9.065 (37.122)	9.599 [55.719]	8.489
Accumulated loans per member	2.313 (18.402)	7.574 [45.455]	6.914
Welfare fund per member	0.829 (21.42)	0.468 [41.277]	5.922
Meso factors (group facilitation)			52.74
Provision of additional social services	-1.351 (-5.236)	-6.491 [68.689]	9.947
Facilitating agency B	3.495 (9.06)	2.502 [26.528]	4.255
Facilitating agency D	-5.564 (-19.859)	-11.631 [96.178]	20.966
Group status: active	-0.709 (-2.029)	-3.385 [30.286]	5.139
Group status: graduated	6.802 (18.192)	8.846 [72.202]	12.432
Macro factors (macroeconomic environment)			25.94
Population density	-0.553 (-39.738)	-0.199 [96.059]	19.469
Rural population	3.13 (26.014)	0.49 [46.502]	6.467

(*) Bates and Granger's (1969) combination of estimates from a between-effects panel model with control covariates for countries, donors, and between/within-cycle effects (between R²: .33, overall R²: .26). The t-statistics for the null hypothesis of no effect are shown in parentheses below each estimated coefficient.

(**) BMA estimates. The probability of affecting profitability in savings groups is shown in brackets below each estimated coefficient.

The control covariates for both the Bayesian and classic estimations were included to account for countries, donors, and between-cycles and within-cycle effects.

The provision of additional social services is associated to a reduction in returns equal to six percentage points on average, while the provision of financial training is associated to an increase in returns of only one percentage point. The latter result is similar to that of Bhutoria and Vignoles (2018), who find modest but positive treatment effects produced by financial education. The limited effect of financial training on returns may arise from the weak causal link between low knowledge and under-saving reported by Karlan et al. (2014), besides the fact that financial education as typically implemented does not necessarily lead to substantial behavior change according to Fernandes et al. (2014). Also in relation to meso variables, group formation has a very low probability of affecting profit generation in savings groups. Spontaneously formed groups, and groups formed by a field officer, village agent, group-paid agent, project-paid agent, unpaid agent, or apprentice have in all cases a probability of less than 4% of being associated with ROS. This finding has important financial implications for development agencies involved in the mobilization of savings groups, because it suggests that the type of agent selected for group formation may not have a large impact on profit generation, and thus development agencies can choose cheaper formation methods without having a negative influence on the financial performance of their groups.

Turning to the association of the macroeconomic environment with profit generation, population density and the percentage of rural population in a country are the most important macroeconomic variables for group performance. Population density explains 19% of profit generation in savings groups, while the percentage of rural population explains 6% of profit generation in the reduced model. An average of three percentage points of higher returns is observed in countries with a more rural population (Table 4). These higher returns show that the model of savings groups provides higher benefits to bottom-of-the-pyramid communities in developing countries with a rural and dispersed population.

The macro findings also indicate that the informal intermediation model of savings groups complements the provision of formal financial services. In remote or sparsely populated areas, formal financial services as insurance and agricultural loans may not be cost effective or available because of the imbalance between the fixed transaction costs of formal financial institutions and the small transactions and low demand of the extreme poor, which cannot be compensated with higher interest rates or with higher premium insurance.

In terms of the micro results, group-level characteristics explain 21% of profit generation. The number of loans outstanding per member is associated to an increase in returns equal to

9.6 percentage points with a probability of 56% (Table 4). This is an expected result, as the lending channel is the main source of profit generation in savings groups, and further indicates that the BMA algorithm was able to properly detect the variables that are related to ROS in savings groups.

Finally, the estimates of the importance of variables at the micro level show that the welfare fund of a group is associated to an increase in returns equal to half of a percentage point with a probability of 41% (Table 4). The purpose of the welfare fund is to offer members grants or interest-free loans to cover emergencies and life-cycle events (Le Polain et al., 2018). However, Maliti (2017) finds that some groups in Tanzania use the welfare fund for loan repayment, a deviation from the original purpose of the welfare fund that can increase the returns of a group at the end of a cycle.

5 Conclusion

Savings groups are self-financed associations that provide access to savings and loans to millions of households around the world. Groups that generate profits have a motivation to continue providing social development services and financial inclusion for the poor; hence, it is important to understand which variables are related to profit generation in savings groups.

This study identified which micro, meso, and macro variables are associated to profit generation in savings groups using the SAVIX, a database with information on more than 200,000 savings groups worldwide. The results indicate that, rather than micro variables linked to internal group characteristics, the meso and macro variables are more relevant for generating profits. The meso variables of group facilitation explain 53% of profits in savings groups, while the macro variables of economic environment explain 26% of profits. The remaining 21% of profits is explained by internal group characteristics, such as loan allocation and the existence of a social welfare fund in a group.

The findings on higher returns in rural and less populated countries highlight that the informal financial model of savings groups is better adapted to serve the rural poor and complements the formal provision of microfinance services, formal insurance, and formal agricultural loans, which may not be available or could not be cost-effective in remote

locations due to barriers of physical access and lack of formal documentation among the extreme poor (Demirgüç-Kunt, Beck, and Honohan, 2008).

The results also indicate that NGOs can have a significant positive or negative influence on the profit generation of savings groups. Specifically, graduated groups show higher returns compared to groups under the active supervision of NGOs, which suggests that the facilitation model of development agencies may not be offering enough flexibility to supervised groups. These results are in line with Boonyabancha (2001), Danquah et al. (2018), Jahns and Wilson (2018), and Gugerty (2019), who recognize that the type of facilitation model implemented by NGOs has a dissimilar impact on profit generation.

The impact of the facilitation model of NGOs is further supported by the finding that a negative effect on returns is observed in groups working with development agency D, whereas a positive effect on returns is observed in groups working with agency B. Both agencies D and B follow a standardized model of savings groups that features 15 to 25 members, weekly meetings, an operational cycle of 9 to 12 months, and the integration of social development programs within a group. Agency B, however, offers more flexibility to the groups by implementing digital platforms that allow members to reduce the frequency of meetings from once a week to once every two weeks. Thus, how a program is implemented can be more important than the program itself, as some implementation strategies encourage success while others lead to unsuccessful savings groups in terms of profit generation.

Future studies can seek to deepen the understanding about the role of the welfare fund as an informal insurance mechanism in savings groups. Identifying the impact on profits of the different development activities—such as those related to training on climate change and agriculture—may also better link financial activities with social programs⁴. Both research lines will shed light on best practices to promote cost-effective financial inclusion through savings groups.

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⁴ See for example the recent machine-learning evidence in Gonzales Martinez (2020).

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Appendix A. Savings Groups

Savings groups are community-based providers of informal financial services in rural and peri-urban areas. Savings groups are formed by 15 to 30 members—usually women—who meet weekly during a cycle of operation that typically lasts 9 to 12 months. Savings group members deposit their mandatory savings into a metal box during the meetings, and afterwards loans are allocated to selected members with the money from the box. Interest rates are fixed by the group. Some groups also own some property like a calculator or a small hut where they hold their meetings. Besides savings and loans, savings groups provide informal insurance to their members by means of a welfare fund that supports members in case of emergencies.

During the cycle of operation, groups keep part of the collected savings as cash in a box due to the lack of demand for loans or the groups' needs to accumulate cash before the payout at the end of the cycle. At the end of the cycle, all the collected funds and earnings are distributed among the members according to their savings balances. Due to the meaningful role of savings groups for poverty alleviation in rural communities, NGOs work with these groups as a platform to promote development and financial inclusion. The Inter-American Development Bank, the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation, CARE, and Oxfam International are among the international donors and development agencies working with savings groups.

The facilitation model promoted by donors and development agencies is based on two common indigenous grassroots financial systems: Rotating Savings and Credit Associations (ROSCAs) and Accumulating Savings and Credit Associations (ASCAs). Facilitated savings groups are promoted and trained by development agencies or by the government (Archer, 2012). International NGOs in collaboration with their local partners have designed their own group models based on the principles of ROSCAs and ASCAs. According to Le Polain et al. (2018), the best-known group models are the Village Savings and Loan Association (VSLA)

initiated by CARE International, and the Savings and Internal Lending Communities (SILC) promoted by Catholic Relief Services.

Participation in a savings group influences members' ability to accumulate capital (Alila, 1998), to execute investments (Hospes, 1995), and to satisfy basic needs (Mayoux and Anand, 1995). The impact of savings groups on the livelihood of its members has been largely measured with non-financial metrics, such as housing quality (Allen, 2006), malnutrition and food security (Vanmeenen, 2010; Brunie et al., 2014; Beaman, Karlan, and Thuysbaert, 2014; LowickiZucca et al.; 2014, Ksoll et al., 2016), improved access to water and sanitation (Vanmeenen, 2010), access to health services (Vanmeenen, 2010; Mutebi et al., 2017), community-led HIV prevention strategies (Mantsios et al., 2018), income-generating activities (Allen, 2006; Ksoll et al., 2016; Flynn and Sumberg, 2018), accumulation of social capital (Ban, Gilligan, and Rieger, 2015), and women's empowerment (Karlan et al., 2017).

The evidence on the impact of savings groups is mixed and seems to be context-dependent; see Gash and Odell (2013) for a survey of results from 53 randomized control trials on savings groups, and Entz, Karsgaard, and Salomons (2016) for a survey of the impact of self-help groups.

Appendix B. Robustness analysis

Ledgerwood, Earne, and Nelson (2013) propose ROS as a metric to measure profits in the SAVIX database, as well as a return on assets (ROA) as a measure of profit generation in relation to member investment. Table A1 shows the results of applying the Bayesian data-mining methods of the study to discover the relationships between ROA and potential macro, meso and micro drivers of profit generation. Table B compares the results for ROA against those obtained for ROS and calculates the difference (D) between the estimates for ROS and ROA.

The estimated results for ROA are similar to those obtained for ROS. Meso variables related to the facilitation mechanisms of NGOs are the most important factors for profit generation when using both ROS and ROA: the importance of meso-variables is equal to 52% when using ROS and is equal to 51% when using ROA. The main difference between the estimates for ROS and ROA at meso-level is only the provision of additional social services, which has a lower importance for ROA (5%) compared to ROS (7.7%). For the rest of the variables, the difference is smaller than 1%.

At micro-level, only the fund utilization rate and the social welfare fund have different estimates between ROS and ROA. The fund utilization rate has an importance of 10.2% for ROA, while for ROS is 1.63%. The social welfare fund has a low importance for ROA (0.57%), compared to ROS (4.57%). At macro-level, the population density of a country is less importance for ROA (10.12%), compared to ROS (15%), but it is still the most important macro-variable related to profit generation. In turn, financial deepening is more important for ROA (2.65%) compared to ROS (1.06%). For the rest of the variables, the difference between the estimates for ROS and ROA are smaller than 1%, and hence it can be concluded that the results are robust to the metric used to measure profit generation in savings groups.

Table B: Bayesian data-mining results

	Bayesian point estimates		Probability of driving financial performance			Importance for profitability (%)		
	ROS	ROA	ROS	ROA	Δ	ROS	ROA	Δ
Micro-factors (group-level characteristics)						21.06	26.52	5.46
Member's attendance	0.0006	0.0000	2.33	2.91	0.58	0.31	0.76	0.45
Dropout rate	0.0104	0.0000	5.35	2.67	-2.69	1.15	0.66	-0.49
Number of loans outstanding per member	9.5990	0.0319	55.72	52.91	-2.81	6.55	6.41	-0.15
Women members in a group	-0.0001	0.0000	1.66	2.52	0.86	0.06	0.23	0.16
Group size	0.0055	0.0000	3.52	5.38	1.86	0.76	1.18	0.42
Accumulated loans per member	7.5745	0.0278	45.45	48.10	2.64	5.34	5.79	0.45
Welfare fund per member	0.4677	0.0000	41.28	2.50	-38.78	4.57	0.57	-4.00
Fund utilization rate	-0.0064	-0.0003	9.49	78.64	69.15	1.63	10.22	8.59
Urban savings groups	0.0656	0.0002	3.64	3.18	-0.46	0.70	0.71	0.01
Meso-factors (group facilitation)						52.00	51.10	-0.91
Provision of additional services	-0.5849	-0.0016	11.36	10.02	-1.34	1.86	1.83	-0.02
Provision of additional social services	-6.4915	-0.0115	68.69	41.17	-27.52	7.68	5.01	-2.66
Provision of additional financial services	1.0472	0.0044	14.42	17.84	3.42	2.15	2.73	0.58
No facilitating agency	0.0117	0.0000	2.71	2.48	-0.23	0.09	0.08	-0.01
Facilitating agency A	0.0515	0.0006	2.65	4.40	1.76	0.43	1.01	0.58
Facilitating agency B	2.5021	0.0091	26.53	27.32	0.79	3.28	3.68	0.40
Facilitating agency C	-1.3077	-0.0035	16.87	13.53	-3.34	2.41	2.29	-0.12
Facilitating agency D	-11.6309	-0.0374	96.18	93.12	-3.06	16.18	15.44	-0.74
Facilitating agency E	-0.4917	-0.0010	7.76	5.85	-1.91	1.42	1.24	-0.19
Group status: active	-3.3854	-0.0106	30.29	31.76	1.48	3.97	4.45	0.49
Group status: graduated	8.8459	0.0256	72.20	70.07	-2.13	9.59	9.84	0.24
Group status: supervised	-0.1522	-0.0004	3.80	3.07	-0.73	0.48	0.44	-0.04
Formation by field officer	-0.0148	-0.0001	2.25	2.47	0.23	0.29	0.52	0.23
Formation by field officer	-0.3563	-0.0008	3.13	2.17	-0.96	0.57	0.48	-0.10
Formation by field officer	-0.0218	0.0000	2.47	2.00	-0.47	0.35	0.01	-0.34
Formation by field officer	-0.0664	-0.0007	2.76	4.86	2.11	0.55	1.13	0.59
Formation by field officer	-0.0173	0.0000	1.95	2.10	0.15	0.14	0.09	-0.05
Formation by field officer	-0.2029	-0.0008	2.80	2.65	-0.15	0.51	0.60	0.09
Formation by field officer	-0.0093	0.0001	2.24	1.96	-0.28	0.04	0.21	0.16
Macro-factors (macro-economic environment)						26.94	22.39	-4.55
Macroeconomic uncertainty	0.0032	0.0000	2.25	2.29	0.04	0.12	0.39	0.27
Inflation rate	0.0006	0.0000	2.45	2.27	-0.18	0.06	0.34	0.27
Age-dependency ratio	0.0020	0.0000	1.85	2.35	0.49	0.17	0.03	-0.14
Inequality	-0.0233	-0.0001	3.40	2.67	-0.73	0.66	0.53	-0.13
Financial deepening	-0.0142	-0.0003	5.26	16.88	11.61	1.06	2.65	1.60
Literacy rate	-0.0134	0.0000	3.81	3.08	-0.73	0.60	0.29	-0.31
GDP per capit	0.0006	0.0000	6.11	4.40	-1.71	1.00	0.92	-0.08
Population density	-0.1987	-0.0005	96.06	78.41	-17.65	15.03	10.12	-4.90
Rural population	0.4897	0.0015	46.50	39.42	-7.08	4.99	4.81	-0.18
Poverty (headcount rate)	-0.0139	0.0000	3.05	3.05	0.00	0.67	0.60	-0.08
GDP growth	0.1558	0.0002	18.63	8.52	-10.12	2.58	1.72	-0.86

(*) In the data-mining models, control variates were included to account for countries, donors, between-cycles and within-cycles effects

Appendix C. Potential explanatory variables considered in the study

Table C: Potential explanatory variables of profit generation in savings groups*

	Description	Justification
Group characteristics		
Members' attendance of group meetings	Members attending meetings as a percentage of active members	Ledgerwood, Earne, and Nelson (2013)
Dropout rate	Dropouts as a percentage of members at formation	Ledgerwood et al. (2013)
Number of loans outstanding per member	Number of loans outstanding over number of active members	Ugbomeh et al. (2008), Lowicki-Zucca et al. (2014)
Women members in the group	Active women as a percentage of active members	Burlando and Canidio (2017)
Group size	Members at formation as a percentage of active members	Bisrat, Kostas, and Feng (2012)
Accumulated loans per member	Cumulative number of loans in the cycle per active member	Ksoll et al. (2016)
Welfare fund per member	Cash in other funds per active member	Calomiris and Rajaraman (1998), Maliti (2017)
Fund utilization rate	Value of loans outstanding as a percentage of total assets	Annan et al. (2013)
Peri-urban savings groups	Dummy variable equal to one for groups in peri-urban regions (zero for rural regions)	Christensen (1993)
Group facilitation		
Provision of additional development services	Dummy variable equal to one for groups that received development services	Beaman, Karlan, and Thuysbaert (2014)
Provision of additional financial services	Dummy variable equal to one for groups that received financial and business training	Beaman et al. (2014)
Provision of additional social services	Dummy variable equal to one for groups that received social development services	Boonyabanha (2001), Green (2019)
No facilitating agency	Dummy variable equal to one for groups without a facilitating agency	Beaman et al. (2014), Sinclair and Singh (2015)
Facilitating agency A	Dummy variable equal to one for groups working with the facilitating agency A	Sinclair and Singh (2015), Green (2019)
Facilitating agency B	Dummy variable equal to one for groups working with the facilitating agency B	Sinclair and Singh (2015), Green (2019)
Facilitating agency C	Dummy variable equal to one for groups working with the facilitating agency C	Sinclair and Singh (2015), Green (2019)
Facilitating agency D	Dummy variable equal to one for groups working with the facilitating agency D	Sinclair and Singh (2015), Green (2019)
Facilitating agency E	Dummy variable equal to one for groups working with the facilitating agency E	Sinclair and Singh (2015), Green (2019)
Status: active	Dummy variable equal to one for groups in an active state	Vanmeenen (2006)
Status: graduated	Dummy variable equal to one for graduated groups	Vanmeenen (2006), Delany and Storchi (2012)
Status: supervised	Dummy variable equal to one for supervised groups	Allen (2010)
Formation by field officer	Dummy variable equal to one for groups formed by a field officer	Muroyiwa (2019)
Formation by village agent	Dummy variable equal to one for groups formed by a village agent	Muroyiwa (2019)
Formation by group-paid agent	Dummy variable equal to one for groups formed by a group-paid agent	Greaney, Kaboski, and Van Leemput (2016)
Formation by project-paid agent	Dummy variable equal to one for groups formed by a project-paid agent	Kast, Meier, and Pomeranz (2018)
Formation by unpaid agent	Dummy variable equal to one for groups formed by an unpaid agent	Thorp et al. (2005)
Formation by apprentice	Dummy variable equal to one for groups formed by an apprentice	Muroyiwa (2019), Thorp et al. (2005)
Formation: spontaneous	Dummy variable equal to one for groups that were formed spontaneously	Thorp et al. (2005)
Macroeconomic variables		
Macroeconomic uncertainty	Average country inflation over past five years	Skinner (1988), Johnson and Rogaly (1997)
Inflation rate	Inflation based on consumer prices (annual %)	Allen (2006), Bisrat, Kostas, and Feng (2012)
Age-dependency ratio	Ratio of dependents (children and elderly) to working-age population	Levenson and Besley (1996)
Inequality	Gini index (World Bank estimate)	Mikesell and Zinser (1973)
Financial deepening	Domestic credit provided by financial sector (percentage of GDP)	Loayza, Schmidt-Hebbel, and Servén (2000)
Literacy rate	Literacy rate, adult total (% of people ages 15 and above)	Mutebi et al. (2017), Steinert et al. (2018)
GDP per capita	Gross domestic product divided by midyear population	Collins (1991), Edwards (1995), Schmidt-Hebbel and Servén (2000)
Population density	People per square kilometer of land area	Christensen, (1993)
Rural population	Population living in rural areas as a percentage of total population	Loayza et al. (2000), Christensen, (1993)
Poverty	Poverty headcount ratio at national poverty lines	Iregui-Bohórquez et al. (2018)
GDP growth	Gross domestic product growth (annual %)	Bouman (1995), Attanasio, Picci, and Scorcu (2000)

(*) The variables related to group characteristics and group facilitation are calculated with the available information in the SAVIX. The source of the macroeconomic variables is the World Bank's database of World Development Indicators.

Appendix D. Bayesian Model Averaging (BMA)

Let y be a measure of profit generation in savings groups and let x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k be the k -potential explanatory variables of y for a sample size of n -groups across a time index t . If y depends on x_i within a linear relationship, then

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \dots + \beta_k x_k + \varepsilon = \mathbf{X}\mathbf{b} + \mathbf{e}, \quad (1)$$

where ε is an i.i.d. Gaussian perturbation with zero mean and variance σ^2 . In the BMA algorithm, the estimates of \mathbf{b} are obtained with a longitudinal linear model with between-cycles effects at group level and fixed effects for countries, donors, and group cycles, this is, uj -binary effects for j countries, donors, and cycles were added to \mathbf{e} in equation 1, and the resultant between-cycles effects (be) estimator of \mathbf{b} is $\hat{\mathbf{b}}_{be} = (\bar{\mathbf{X}}'\bar{\mathbf{X}})^{-1}\bar{\mathbf{X}}'\bar{\mathbf{y}}$.

Fixed effects were not used at group level because fixed effects applied in longitudinal data require considering differences over time and would have involved getting rid of the distinctive specific characteristics of higher-level units (see Bell and Jones, 2015). The unbalanced information in the SAVIX—in addition to the short time span and the focus of the study on the differences between savings groups—implies that using fixed effects at group level would have eliminated the effects of interest among groups and would have left only low informative within-cycle effects across time.

Controlling the group-level heterogeneity with a random-effects model also did not seem appropriate, since, as noted by Mundlak (1978), the random-effects model assumes exogeneity of regressors with respect to the random individual effects; i.e., assuming that the unobserved variables not considered in the performance model are not related to the explanatory variables considered in the model, an assumption that seems too strong given the limited number of available control covariates in the SAVIX. Both reasons led to the use of a between-effects model to control for the heterogeneity of savings groups in the SAVIX database.

In order to identify which potential explanatory variables are relevant to profit generation, the study applied BMA to estimate equation (1) with different combinations of explanatory variables and then calculated the probability of each variable being important to profit generation in savings groups. The algorithm exploits the fact that the evidence about the importance of a covariate can be approximated with the (penalized) log-likelihood of the equations where a specific covariate appears: given the k -variables that could explain profit generation, the model space of all the possible combinations of these regressors is defined by the power set $\wp(k)$,

$$\wp(k) = \{\{\emptyset\}, \{x_1\}, \{x_2\}, \dots, \{x_k\}, \{x_1, x_2\}, \dots, \{x_1, \dots, x_k\}\}. \quad (2)$$

The number of models in the space is defined by the cardinality of the power set

$$|\wp(k)| = \sum_{p=0}^k \binom{k}{p} = 2^k, \quad (3)$$

from a Bayesian perspective, the classical likelihood function

$$\ell(\beta, \sigma^2 | y, \mathbf{X}) = (2\pi\sigma^2)^{-n/2} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{2\sigma^2} (y - \mathbf{X}\beta)^\top (y - \mathbf{X}\beta)\right], \quad (4)$$

can be expressed in a gamma/Gaussian form in order to obtain Bayesian estimators through the use of a natural Gaussian conjugate for β and an inverse gamma conjugate for σ^2 . The prior distribution of β is

$$\beta|\sigma^2, \mathbf{X} \sim \mathcal{N}_{k+1}(\tilde{\beta}, \sigma^2 \mathbf{M}^{-1}), \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{M} is a symmetric positive definite matrix of dimensions $(k+1) \times (k+1)$. The prior of σ^2 is

$$\sigma^2|\mathbf{X} \sim \mathcal{IG}(a, b), \quad a, b > 0. \quad (6)$$

The Bayesian point estimators of β and σ^2 , under quadratic loss, are the posterior mean of $P(\beta|\sigma^2, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{X})$ and $P(\sigma^2|\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{X})$,

$$\mathbb{E}[\beta|\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{X}] = \mathbb{E}[\mathbb{E}(\beta|\sigma^2, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{X})|\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{X}] \quad (7)$$

$$= (\mathbf{M} + \mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{X})^{-1} \{(\mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{X})\hat{\beta} + \mathbf{M}\tilde{\beta}\}. \quad (8)$$

The selection of the hyper-parameter values and \mathbf{M} affect the Bayesian estimates. To decrease the impact of this selection, Zellner (1986) suggests the use of g-priors based on a conditional Gaussian prior for β ,

$$\beta|\sigma^2, \mathbf{X} \sim \mathcal{N}_{k+1}(\tilde{\beta}, g\sigma^2 (\mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{X})^{-1}), \quad (9)$$

and an improper Jeffrey's prior $P(\sigma^2|\mathbf{X}) \propto \sigma^{-2}$ for σ^2 . With Zellner's g-priors, the Bayesian estimators of the effects of the micro/meso/macro variable on the performance of savings groups are:

$$\mathbb{E}[\beta|\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{X}] = \frac{1}{g+1} (\tilde{\beta} + g\hat{\beta}), \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbb{E}[\sigma^2|\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{X}] = \frac{s^2 + (\tilde{\beta} - \hat{\beta})^T \mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{X} (\tilde{\beta} - \hat{\beta}) / (g+1)}{n-2}. \quad (11)$$

See, e.g., Gill (2014) or Fokoue and Ly (2014).

The probability of \mathbf{X} affecting \mathbf{y} can be estimated with the marginal likelihood of a model conditional on an information set \mathcal{D} :

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{M}_i|\mathcal{D}) \propto (\mathbf{y} - \bar{\mathbf{y}})' (\mathbf{y} - \bar{\mathbf{y}})^{\frac{n-1}{2}} (1+g)^{\frac{k_i}{2}} \left(1 - \frac{g}{1+g}\right)^{-\frac{n-1}{2}}. \quad (12)$$

When the baseline model is the null model \mathbf{M}_0 , with no independent variables, then $2\log B_0_j$, where B_0_j is the Bayes factor for the null model \mathbf{M}_0 against the models of interest \mathbf{M}_j . If $\mathbf{M}_1, \mathbf{M}_2, \dots, \mathbf{M}_k$ models are being considered and each of $\mathbf{M}_1, \dots, \mathbf{M}_k$ is compared in turn with \mathbf{M}_0 , yielding Bayes factors B_{10}, \dots, B_{k0} , then the posterior probability of \mathbf{M}_j , $j = 1, 2, \dots, k$, is

$$\mathbb{P}(\mathcal{M}_j|\mathcal{D}) = \frac{\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{M}_j|\mathcal{D}) \mathbb{P}(\mathcal{M}_j)}{\sum_{i=1}^k \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{M}_i|\mathcal{D}) \mathbb{P}(\mathcal{M}_i)}. \quad (13)$$

The Bayesian estimator is obtained by adding the estimates of β_j in each j-model, weighted by the posterior probability of each model being true, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\beta}_{BD} &:= \mathbb{E}(\theta|\mathcal{D}, \theta \neq 0), \\ &\propto \sum \sum_{\mathcal{A}_0} \mathbb{E}(\theta|\mathcal{D}, \mathcal{M}_j) \mathbb{P}(\mathcal{M}_j|\mathcal{D}). \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

The probability of each variable $\mathbf{x}_k \in \mathbf{X}$ affecting profit generation in savings groups is obtained by adding the probabilities of the \mathbf{M}_j models where each \mathbf{x}_k covariate appears:

$$\mathbb{P}(x_k|\mathcal{D}) = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{J}} \mathbb{P}(\mathcal{M}_j|\mathcal{D}). \quad (15)$$

See Kass and Raftery (1995), Hoeting et al. (1999), or Koop (2003).

The marginal likelihood of equation 12—which is crucial to estimate the probability of each variable affecting profits—depends on the hyper-parameter g that represents the degree of prior uncertainty. Different options have been suggested to elicit this prior (Zeugner and Feldkircher, 2015): Kass and Wasserman (1995) suggest $g = 1/n$, which implies assigning an amount of information to the prior equivalent to 1 observation in the dataset and hence this elicitation is denominated the Unit Information Prior (UIP). Foster and George (1994) and George and Foster (2000) propose the use of the Risk Inflation Criterion (RIC) $g = 1/k^2$, while Fernández, Ley, and Steel (2001) suggest $g = (\max(n, k^2))^{-1}$, i.e., the maximum between the UIP and the RIC. Finally, Marin and Robert (2007) state that $g = 1$ implies assigning the same weight to the prior compared to the data set.

In the case of the SAVIX database there is a large number of n -savings groups; thus, if $g = 1/n$ then $g \approx 0$ and an extremely low penalty will be applied to models with the UIP, an approach not recommended by Ley and Steel (2009). On the other hand, Ciccone and Jarociski (2010) demonstrate also that a large g may not be robust to noise innovations and risks overfitting, if the noise component plays a substantial role in the data, as is the case of the SAVIX. Thus, to deal with the relevant noise component in the SAVIX, a value of $g = .01$ was chosen to render a coefficient distribution tight around the priors. These priors were chosen based on the Laplace uncertainty principle, i.e., by assuming that all possible events were equiprobable (Gurov, 2004). Accordingly, a low prior inclusion probability of $1/k$ was assigned to all the k -potential explanatory variables of profit generation.

In the estimations, 10,000 iterations of the Markov chain Monte Carlo model composition (MC³) were run and a burn-in of 1,000 iterations was discarded from the chain. The large number of iterations was chosen because Feldkircher and Zeugner (2009) argue that the smaller the g prior, the less concentrated is the posterior model probability distribution, and therefore the MCMC sampler must be run with many more iterations in order to achieve meaningful results.

Finally, to compare the complete model obtained with the BMA algorithm with a reduced regression model with the most important variables, a Bayes factor was calculated as the ratio of marginal likelihoods of the reduced model \mathcal{M}_r to the complete model \mathcal{M}_g :

$$BF_{r,g} = \frac{p(y|\mathcal{M}_r)}{p(y|\mathcal{M}_g)}. \quad (16)$$

The Bayes factors $BF_{r,g}$ measure the strength of evidence of model \mathcal{M}_r against model \mathcal{M}_g . Kass and Raftery (1995) suggest the following interpretation of the values of Bayes factors: very strong evidence when $BF_{r,g} > 150$, strong evidence when $20 < BF_{r,g} \leq 150$, positive and substantial evidence when $3 < BF_{r,g} \leq 20$, and evidence not worth mentioning when $1 < BF_{r,g} \leq 3$.